

TECHNOLOGY OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS

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Abstract: This article discusses the question of finding the most priority ways to alleviate water shortages, including the widespread adoption of water-saving technologies in agriculture, especially in irrigated agricultural fields. General information about drip irrigation technology is also provided.

Keywords: drop, agriculture, water resources, innovation, technique, technology, pool, defecation, system.

It is known that the agricultural sector is the largest user of water in the whole world. Therefore, the entire scientific community emphasizes the efficient use of water in agriculture, especially in irrigated agricultural fields, including the widespread introduction of water-saving technologies, as the most priority way to alleviate water shortages.

80% of the consumed water resources are formed on the territory of neighboring countries. Effective use of Uzbekistan's water resources, especially in order to alleviate the water shortage that has been increasing in recent years, is the wide introduction of water-saving systems of crop irrigation and expansion of the possibilities of using modern technologies in the management of water resources. it is permissible to admit that he is taking the initiative among the countries of the region.

In the last five years, a number of decrees and decisions have been adopted by President Sh.Mirziyoyev on the development of the water sector, the introduction of water-saving technologies, and as a result, state subsidies have been allocated to encourage agricultural producers who have introduced new irrigation technologies. the introduction of the mechanism, the creation of a number of benefits for agricultural producers made a fundamental turn in the development of irrigated agriculture. As a result of the attention of the state leadership, the improvement of the necessary legal norms and the consistent application in practice, the scope of introducing water-saving irrigation systems in our country has increased dramatically in recent years. In 2021 alone, the areas where water-saving technologies have been introduced will increase by 5 times and cover 22% of the total irrigated areas, and in the next five to seven years, this indicator is set to reach 50%. The Parliament of our country is also conducting large-scale work on improving the legislation in the field of water management.

As the head of our state emphasized the need to approach every issue with science and experience, advanced modern technologies were brought from foreign countries, and their specialists were involved. Due to the year-by-year expansion of the areas where these technologies are introduced, many enterprises have been established in our country, and the production of irrigation system equipment has been started in local conditions.

Now, there is a need for local personnel who build modern water-saving irrigation systems and provide them with service services. At the same time, the issues of creative approach to these irrigation systems, their improvement, adaptation to the unique soil and climate conditions of Uzbekistan are becoming more relevant day by day, and this is required by life itself.

At the present time, when climate change has become a global problem, the efficient use of water resources has become the agenda. In addition, the demand for water in Uzbekistan is increasing due to the wasteful use of natural water, which may exhaust the limited resources of mankind, the continuous increase in the number of people and consumption according to the laws of population, and high economic growth rates.

The growing population of the world, including Uzbekistan, causes the demand for food products to increase year by year. In a situation where the available amounts of water resources, which are the main source of food production, are decreasing, the issue of developing effective methods of their use, economical use of existing water resources is becoming more urgent day by day. In such conditions, the use of water-saving technologies of crop irrigation is being widely implemented in most countries of the world in order to use water sparingly without wasting water. In this regard, countries such as Israel, Japan, Jordan, China, USA, Italy, Turkey, Greece (Greece), Australia and India have achieved great results.

Located in the center of the Asian continent, thousands of kilometers away from the ocean and seas, our country is located in a dry and hot region, which is one of the only 2 countries in the world where it is necessary to cross the borders of at least 2 other countries to access the world ocean. As mentioned above, in the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where the waters of the main rivers flow from trans-border areas, the issue of effective use of water resources is considered a particularly urgent issue.

Due to the excessive use of water by the extensive agriculture of our country, the problem of shortage of water resources primarily affects the water supply of irrigated areas, and this effect is increasing year by year. In such conditions, the use of water-saving technologies of crop irrigation will further increase the value of these blessings.

For this purpose, with the initiatives of the President, in the last five years, the state has paid great attention to the widespread introduction of water-saving technologies of crop irrigation. In particular, a number of benefits, such as exemption from taxes and allocation of subsidies by the state, were created for agricultural producers who introduced water-saving irrigation systems. As a

result, the areas where water-saving technologies are used in our republic are expanding year by year. In this process, of course, there is an increasing need for qualified national specialists who implement water-saving irrigation systems, use them, and provide service.

Training of qualified local personnel for the field of water management, improvement of the system of improving their qualifications, development of mutual cooperation between education, science, and production sectors, and development of scientific achievements and know-how the need to introduce the issue is one of the most important strategic tasks of our country.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, which is located in an arid region, agriculture is the sector that consumes the most water. About 90% of available water resources are used for agricultural production. In recent years, the state in Uzbekistan has given great importance to the effective use of available water resources based on the widespread introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies in the irrigation of agricultural crops.

Drip irrigation - water purified by special filters is given to the soil in the form of drops through droppers, and it is a (local) moistening of the stratum corneum where the root system of the plant is located.

The water storage part of the system consists of ponds, clarifiers or cisterns, the water purification part consists of sand, disc or mesh filters, the water supply part consists of pumping devices, head and distribution pipes, the water straightening part consists of various valves, valves and fittings, the irrigation part consists of drip hoses or tapes. will consist of In addition, drip irrigation systems can include fertilizing devices and automatic control equipment. Fertilizing devices consist of devices for preparing fertilizer solutions and adding them to water, and automatic control equipment consists of a control computer and various sensors.

When surface water is used as a source of water for a drip irrigation system, the composition of the system does not change much, only a pool - a cooler is added to the composition, and the other parts are the usual pump device, filter, fertilizing device, head and distribution pipes, connectors (faucet and fittings), a drip hose consists of parts such as drippers.

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A schematic general view of the drip irrigation system for use in the drip irrigation system is illustrated in Fig. 1 for the case where water is taken from an underground water source. Drip irrigation system consists of a water source, pump assembly, fertilizer, filter (sand), filter (disc and mesh), main pipe, distribution pipe, pressure regulator (faucet), irrigation hose, drippers. found

Depending on the location of the irrigated fields and the quality of the used water, there may be other types of parts included in the system.

Drip irrigation systems include several parts, namely water storage, purification, delivery, distribution, distribution and irrigation parts.

Depending on the location of the system and the quality of the water used, the types and number of elements included in the system may be different.

Irrigation water is delivered under pressure through pipes to each plant or a row of plants, and it provides the plant's water demand during the growing season. In this way, mineral fertilizers can be applied to the soil together with water.

1 - picture. Scheme of drip irrigation system

It has been determined that the application of mineral fertilizers dissolved in irrigation water gives the opportunity to save nitrogen fertilizers by 44-57%. In the case of drops, the water given to the root layer of the plant is absorbed into the soil layer by capillaries. In this case, the effect of gravity is very small. Wetting takes place under the influence of capillary forces.

The main structures of the drip irrigation system are the pond-cooling system, pump installation, water purification filters, and facilities that supply the fertilizer solution to the system. Water ponds will be organized for continuous supply of water to cultivated fields where drip irrigation is planned. A pond built for a drip irrigation system can also serve to cool or raise the temperature of water at the same time. Therefore, the ponds are arranged in such a way that they also serve as a cooling system at the same time. The pond - the clarifier serves to retain the turbidity of the irrigation water (on the basis of the water clarifier) and to maintain a certain amount of the irrigation water. In practice, types of pond-coolers with earth core, concrete, reinforced concrete, metal and

geomembrane coating are used (Fig. 2).

a)

b)

2 – picture. Appearances of pond softeners in drip irrigation
a) a large pool covered with a geomembrane; b) a small pool covered with a geomembrane

The pool is built on the basis of digging the ground at a certain depth and leveling the shores and bottom. In order to reduce the amount of earthworks, it is necessary to arrange the ponds-coolers semi-deep, and their banks semi-elevated.

In this case, the soil from the digging of the pond is laid on the shores of the pond, and the shores are raised. Pools with the same base of the bottom and the top of the pool can be made higher in advance by installing steel-concrete or metal-clad constructions. In order to prevent the water from being absorbed into the ground and wasted, the bottom and banks of the pond-salator are waterproofed with coatings. Concrete iron - concrete, metal and geomembranes (polyethylene film) are used as such coatings. It is advisable to determine the dimensions of the pond - clarifier based on the design water consumption of the irrigation system, taking into account the turbidity level of the water to be clarified, based on the possibilities of allocating land for the location of the pool, and introducing it in several sectional views. will be. It is considered advisable to place the pond-cooler near the power grid of the field, at a distance where water supply pipes are consumed as little as possible. The size of the pool is determined on the basis of the condition that it can completely cool the water and store enough water for at least one watering. For example, if the volume of water used to irrigate a 10-hectare fruit garden once is taken as a basis (50-60 m³ per 1 ha), then the volume of the built-up pond-cooler can be taken as 500-

600 m³. Covering the bottom and walls of the pool prevents water from seeping into the soil unnecessarily and makes it possible to use the available water efficiently.

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